

Impact of failure rates, lot definitions and scheduling of upstream processes on the productivity of continuous integrated bioprocesses

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: The failure rates and the scheduling of bioprocesses have a substantial impact on process performance and economics but are often overlooked and neglected. Integrated continuous biomanufacturing is more flexible in respect to scheduling and the impact of failures can be reduced by appropriate scheduling and lot definitions.

RESULTS: In this work, we used a Monte Carlo approach on an integrated continuous biomanufacturing process with varying daily failure rates in the upstream and scheduling scenarios for seed fermentation (N-1 stage) to quantify the impact on the actual productive uptime of the integrated process. The optimum targeted production time in the continuous upstream ranges between 45 and 90 days depending on the daily failure rate and the lot definition used for the process. We showed that a minimal flexibility for planning of the seed fermentation is necessary to harvest the full potential of integrated continuous biomanufacturing. A comparison with batch manufacturing in the upstream processing showed a higher productive uptime for continuous biomanufacturing regardless of daily failure rates. Computation of productive uptime for different lot definitions showed that a daily lot definition only shows a loss of 3% to a maximum of 5% productivity, depending on the daily failure rate, compared to a real-time release approach.

CONCLUSIONS: With this study, we provide a decision-making tool for the scheduling of upstream processes and implementation of integrated continuous biomanufacturing taking failure into account, showing the extent to which planning of flexibility and batch definitions influence the productivity of continuous integrated bioprocesses.

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INTRODUCTION

Continuous manufacturing is still in its infancy in the biotech sector mainly due to concerns for process stability, validation and quality, regulatory compliance and risk mitigation.^{1–3} There is no rational understanding of how process failures may affect process economics and how they are affected by the scheduling of process trains. Continuous cell culture in perfusion mode is a crucial process intensification step for increased production capacities in a given volume.^{4–6} In perfusion cultures a population of producing cells is maintained by constantly removing culture supernatant, bleeding off cells and constantly adding fresh media.⁷ Efforts for integrated continuous manufacturing for the whole production train have to include downstream purification, where semi-continuous operations like periodic counter-current chromatography as well as truly continuous unit operations such as continuous precipitation for capture or polishing are employed.^{5,8–10}

Despite clear evidence of the economic benefits, the flexibility for manufacturing and readily available upstream and downstream equipment for continuous processing, the transition to continuous biomanufacturing is in its early stages. Continuous integrated manufacturing comes with better economics and reduced facility footprint.^{4,6,8} While continuous processing has

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been realized for small-molecule pharmaceutical production, the field of biotechnology is still reluctant. This is due to the high uncertainties connected with biological systems and risk assessment for continuous biomanufacturing is still an unknown territory for the biopharmaceutical industry.¹¹ In addition, the high investment costs for setting up new processes, and the already available facilities for batch-wise production of biopharmaceuticals hinder implementation further.¹² Nevertheless, the US Food and Drug Administration is taking steps to facilitate implementation of continuously produced drugs in the biopharmaceutical industry to improve product quality, reduce drug shortages, reduce costs for pharmaceuticals and implement automated monitoring for implementation of a quality-by-design approach^{13,14} and has released draft guidance for continuous biomanufacturing.¹⁵ Batch-wise and continuous manufacturing facilities must comply with the same quality standards, but a continuous process requires more sophisticated scheduling, monitoring tools, preferably on-line or in-line, and a higher degree of automation that can detect issues and react before a failure even occurs.^{4,9}

Failure in a batch-defined setting is connected to one batch, whereas failure of a 'batch' in a continuous setting can mean a specific quantity or timeframe depending on the process definition.^{13,16–18} Moreover, in an interconnected continuous manufacturing setup, a 'batch' failure can occur upstream, downstream or both. Hence, finding clear management strategies for handling failures and quantifying the potential impact is of particular importance.

A failure rate of production lots can be caused by equipment failure, human error or inability to meet specifications.¹⁹ While preventative measures like equipment qualifications or personnel training can be applied to reduce them in a more general term, product-specific failures for not meeting certain specifications like aggregation levels or specific glycosylation have to be addressed case by case and are governed by the robustness of the product in terms of formulation, manufacturing procedure or analytical methodology.²⁰ While the failure rate definition for batch production is easily done with a statement of how many lots failed in comparison to how many succeeded, the definition for continuous manufacturing is more complicated as the failure may only apply to a certain quantity which can be isolated and discarded assuming proper monitoring and control strategies or can mean a catastrophic failure where the system needs to be restarted.^{21,22}

To ensure detection of failures, a more intense and accurate online monitoring and control instrumentation is required for increased product quality assurance in real time, which is amenable to real-time release testing approaches.^{16,23–27} Real-time release ensures minimal product loss and an enhanced process reliability. One important parameter for lot description is the residence time distribution, dictating the spread of process disturbances and their traceability. A narrower residence time distribution results in less product lost in case of a failure.^{13,28}

Failure rates and their impact in continuous manufacturing are hard to estimate and data are scarce especially for downstream operations, but for example Oyebolu *et al.* showed a continuous mAb process event, where ATF filter failure occurs with a probability of 2% causing a replacement of filters and perfusate discard of the consecutive 24 h of runtime.²⁹ However, occurrence rates and concrete impacts may vary significantly depending on the facility and expertise of the manufacturer, and whether the failure occurs upstream or downstream.³⁰ However, to the best of our knowledge, an investigation of how much product has to be discarded

in the case of a failure and if this is significant enough in comparison to the effort of implementing real-time release has never been done.

Therefore, we evaluated the impact of different frequencies of batch failures at different points in biopharmaceutical production with a focus on upstream manufacturing including the seed fermentation stage (N-1) and scheduling of the N-1 stage. We further assumed a conservative approach in which a failure in the upstream process leads to a necessary restart of the perfusion process which takes several days. For downstream operations we assumed that a restart in the downstream process will lead to a temporary shutdown of 24 h. We used estimated failure rates²⁷ and utilized a Monte Carlo method to simulate the impact of different control strategies and lot definitions. This study quantifies the benefit of real-time release and the effects of scheduling of the N-1 stage as well as the facility flexibility on the loss of product and productive uptime of the entire facility.

EXPERIMENTAL

Process definition for Monte Carlo simulation

The process was defined as a day-by-day simulation of failure rates and a day-to-day allocation of possible failure events. The simulation was set up using a custom-built simulation in visual basic for applications run in Microsoft Excel and simulated a day-by-day run, accumulating 30 000 simulated runs for each data point and calculating a total uptime of the facility. The parameter uptime describes the ratio where the facility is actually productive and is defined by Eqn (1):

$$\text{Uptime} = \frac{t_{\text{total}} - t_{\text{start}} - t_{\text{flex}}}{t_{\text{total}}} \quad (1)$$

where t_{total} represents the total time, t_{start} the necessary start-up time for the upstream fermentation and t_{flex} the time loss due to possible scheduling conflicts according to the scenario used for facility flexibility. The advantage of this key figure is that it is independent of scale and product, and can be translated to known product facilities. Additionally, it can be easily integrated into a future economic evaluation reducing the productive time of the respective process train.

The setup of the Monte Carlo simulation is depicted in Fig. 1, showing the start of each individual simulation, looping through a daily simulation and failure decision, adding the respective time penalty and saving it into the ensemble of individual runs for the specific daily failure rate and target runtime. From this ensemble in the database a total productive uptime is calculated, subtracting all non-productive days as described above.

Failure rates were estimated from the 15th Annual Report of Biopharmaceutical Manufacturing Capacity and Production.²⁷ A failure rate was attributed to each day individually and a range of failure rates was calculated as the estimation of failure rates from the literature is limited.

The process was defined as a seed fermentation (N-1), an upstream perfusion process with no interconnection to subsequent downstream operations, or one or more subsequent downstream operations. The seed fermentation was selected to be run in parallel with the upstream perfusion process if the next perfusion process starts on the planned day (and does not terminate early). Failure in the upstream leads to a complete process termination in our simulation as this simulation should inform the

Figure 1. (A) Depiction of the downtime associated with a termination of the process on schedule with the N-1 started in advance of the process end, and an unscheduled termination of the process resulting in a larger downtime due to the start of the N-1 stage when the process terminates due to a failure. (B) Flow scheme of the Monte Carlo simulation depicting the simulation taking daily failure rates and target runtime as input, simulating individual runs with respective failure rates and reporting an average uptime across all simulated runs.

conservative stance on the impact on current implementation scenarios, and this reflects the current approach to batch production. Failure in the downstream does not lead to a complete termination in the model, but to a diversion of the production to waste for the time of the process interruption.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Estimation of failure rates

Information on failure rates is limited in the literature, and only little information can be found on the cause of failures for batch production.²⁷ Information on failure rates for continuously operated manufacturing is not available at all and was estimated from batch failure rates. According to this survey, we can expect a batch failure rate due to contamination of 2.3%, and failures due to operator error, equipment failure or material failure of 1.5%, 1.4% and 0.6%, respectively. Additionally, there were failures due to failing to meet the specifications of 1.0%, cross-product contamination of 0.4% and other reasons of 0.4% (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Reasons for batch failure for batches below a size of 1000 L. (Redrawn with data from the 15th Annual Report and Survey of Biopharmaceuticals Manufacturing Capacity and Production 2018.²⁷)

While the definition of failure rate as a ratio between successful and unsuccessful batches works for batch-mode operation, the definition of failure rate for continuous production must follow a

different paradigm. In principle, continuous production is intended for an indefinite process. In reality, achieved process durations of 30 days or sometimes even shorter are already branded as continuous. However, the traditional batch definition can no longer be applied for continuous processes as material produced before a failure can still be used in the final product. This issue is also deeply connected with the definition of a 'lot' in regulatory terms for continuous products, as lots define the amount of material that needs to be discarded in the case of a failure. It is usually propagated that the ultimate goal for overcoming this issue in continuous manufacturing would be the application of real-time release, based on a sophisticated monitoring strategy and an advanced control regime.

The common redefinition of batches or lots for continuous operation is to treat a specific timeframe as lot, where the timeframe could be a minute, an hour or a day, depending on the monitoring capabilities implemented. In the case of a daily lot, the production material from the whole process train would be collected at the end for one day, and that collection can be tested for release as usual, or can be released automatically through a real-time release approach. This day-by-day definition will be used in this work to estimate the impact of failure rates on a daily basis on the whole-process productivity. In addition, we assume a conservative approach meaning that a failure of the culture leads to a termination of the process and a restart. This is a conservative approach that can be implemented today and we are aware that current and future developments might allow better process control.^{9,31–37}

This continuous day-by-day definition and potential failures necessitate the handling of a dynamic schedule in the facility and the willingness to deal with early process terminations and restarting the continuous culture not only in a fixed schedule. In batch mode, the culture will run between 9 and 15 days in the production stage and will be discarded at the end when it is not suitable. In continuous mode, it has to be expected that some of the cultures, intended for 30 days or more, will not make it to the end. However, the material processed in the days before early termination will still go through purification, polishing and into a final product while the continuous culture will be restarted as soon as possible.

For transferring the batch failure rates into daily failure rates in a continuous setup, we decided to split the aforementioned risks mentioned in the survey into two groups. The first group consists of the contamination risk and the cross-product contamination risks which are more likely whenever there is a need for manipulation, for example during setup and inoculation at the start of the process, resulting in an estimated first day contamination risk of 2.7%. The second group consists of all other reasons, which can occur each day during cultivation, where equipment and materials can fail, and the operator can make errors. The accumulated total batch failure rate for these events can be estimated to be 4.9%. To transform this number to a daily failure risk we assume that the reported batches in this survey will have an average runtime of 12 days, and that these risks are evenly spread throughout the batch process. This translates then to a daily failure rate of 0.4% for all days during the production, and a failure rate of about 3% for the first day during setup of the process (including the contamination risk). We are aware that this translation of failure rates to the continuous system is prone to large systematic errors. The real failure rates could be substantially different for various reasons. Therefore, we chose to investigate a wide range of

daily failure rates, ranging from 0.01% daily representing an exceptionally stable system, up to 2% daily, representing an exceptionally unstable system.

In addition, we assume in our models a completely uniform risk associated for the failure of different kinds for each day during production except the first day. Whereas this might be reasonable for operator errors and equipment failures, the chance for material failure or the failure to meet specifications might not be completely uniform. The culture might slowly drift out of specifications with time, and materials like plastics might age during the runtime and therefore have a higher associated risk later in the process than earlier. Unfortunately, there are no reliable data available in the literature to assess the nonlinearity of these risks, and our analysis might have to be revisited regarding these factors in the future when and if more data are available from industrial production plants running continuous manufacturing. For now, we intend to capture this variation sufficiently in our large range of daily failure rates investigated for this study, while more detailed and possible influence on specific process choices will have to be implemented in future studies when specific daily failure rate data are available. In this work we focus on catastrophic failures in production that lead to a restart of the system, as the data available are for catastrophic batch failures. Intermittent deviations where the process can be readjusted will be followed up in future publications as they require a detailed mechanistic or statistic process model of a specific process.

To enable easy translation of the results of this study to any production scenario or specific product, we calculate the actual uptime for the whole process train where the process train produces material. This uptime can be used regardless of facility size, product titre and yields in the process. Known parameters for a specific process can be easily adapted for a risk-including yield through the use of the planned uptime and the risk-reduced uptime reported in this study. This uptime can be further used to calculate the economics of a process including specific risk management strategies and expected failure rates. The expression of uptime is independent of cost, titre and scale and therefore more useful for a general investigation on the influence of risk and how to manage such risk successfully, while still keeping the possibility of integrating this key figure directly into any cost calculation.

Influence of failure rate on scheduling and uptime in perfusion cultures and associated N-1 fermentations

To start the investigation, we modelled a perfusion culture and the connected pre-culture (N-1) which is needed for inoculation for the perfusion process. The perfusion process is planned for a certain maximum process runtime but might terminate early in the case of a failure. We modelled target process runtimes of between 7 and 320 days, where a shorter target runtime means that the process will more likely terminate as planned, while a longer target runtime naturally will lead to more early process terminations due to failure. In the case of a failure, the process is stopped, all material on the day of the failure goes to waste and all product produced before that will be further processed.

When the process reaches the planned maximum runtime, we assume that the N-1 stage is already finished as it can be planned to be run in parallel to the last days of the perfusion culture, whereas if the process terminates early, the perfusion reactor has to wait for the inoculum to be prepared. We assume that the N-1 stage will run for 9 days, which represents an additional downtime of the perfusion reactor in the case of early termination

due to a failure. In addition, we assume that the cleaning, setup and start of the perfusion in the production reactor take 3 days which are not used for production, but can be accomplished in parallel to the N-1 stage. In summary in this first simulation, the time between consecutive batches is 3 days if the perfusion culture reached the target process runtime, whereas the time between batches is increased to 9 days in the case of an unexpected early termination due to a failure (Fig. 1(A)).

We simulated individual runs using Monte Carlo simulation, testing each day for a failure of the process with an associated daily failure rate and an increased failure rate for day one as described above. The simulation records each individual run and how long the productive time is and records the associated downtime for each run individually (either 3 days for a run completing on schedule or 9 days for a run terminating early due to a failure). The recorded runs are then used to calculate an average productive uptime across all runs. A process flow scheme for illustration of the simulation is presented in Fig. 1(B).

We simulated the uptime for different planned maximum process runtimes, from day one to the targeted end with daily failure rates between 0.01% and 2% (Fig. 3(A)). The uptime is improved with longer target runtimes with a markedly flattening curve for planned maximum process times longer than 90 days. When choosing 60 days planned maximum process time instead of 30 days we gain an additional 5–10% uptime depending on the daily failure rate. We gain almost nothing when changing from a 120 days planned process time to 150 days. As mentioned before, this is significant as some risk

factors might not be linearly spread across the whole range, like genetic drift or the failure rate of plastics and other materials. From these curves, it is reasonable to argue for a planned runtime of 90 days regardless of daily failure rate. The gain in additional uptime is negligible for longer timeframes, and the uncertainty of the involved risks will increase with longer runtimes. Interestingly the curves in this simulation do not show an optimum, and a longer targeted runtime is always better. This is easily explained by the average time penalty for each day longer in the model. Each additional day of targeted runtime has an associated potential time penalty of 6 additional downtime days multiplied by the failure rate of that specific simulation (Eqn (2)). As long as the daily failure rate is below 16.7% (1 day additional productivity/6 days potential downtime) an additional day in the targeted runtime will always result in a higher average uptime (Eqn (3)).

$$[\text{average time penalty}] = [\text{time penalty for failure}] \times [\text{failure rate per day}] \quad (2)$$

$$[\text{breakeven failure rate}] = [\text{potentially gained productive time}] / [\text{time penalty for failure}] \quad (3)$$

Depending on the targeted process time and the daily risk, a larger or smaller portion of processes will be terminated early (Fig. 3(B)). Even for small failure rates of below 0.05% per day, the facility will have to accommodate for 10% of the runs

Figure 3. (A) Uptime for a perfusion culture with a planned process time and daily failure rates with a dedicated N-1 with instant availability. (B) Necessary target runtime for a specific goal of uptime of a perfusion reactor for a given daily failure rate of the process. (C) Utilization of the N-1 reactor for a given failure rate and targeted runtime. (D) Percentage of unexpected/unplanned N-1 runs in relation to the targeted anticipated runtime and daily failure rate. The data represent a total of ca 500 000 individual simulated runs.

terminating early for a planned maximum production of 90 days. When we assume the transferability of batch failure rates as described above, resulting in a failure rate of about 0.3% per day we already have to accommodate for about 25% of the runs being terminated earlier than 90 days. Even under conservative failure assumptions of 0.1% or lower, a significant portion of perfusion processes will not make it to the targeted process end. Hence, early process termination has to be expected for continuous processes and needs to be planned for.

We think that this demonstrates the importance of a different viewpoint on failure rates when discussing continuous processes, as a significant portion of processes will terminate early, even if risks are reduced as much as possible.

These data can also be used for process design, as we can adjust the target runtime to a specific goal of uptime in a production facility with an associated cost in the organization due to the unscheduled starts of N-1 cultures. This is an organizational burden on management, as resources have to be reallocated quickly, both in equipment, as the N-1 stage has to be available, and in personnel. In many cases, running the N-1 equipment, or even having one dedicated instrument for the N-1 stage, is cheaper than postponing the start of the next cycle in the production reactor itself, but designing continuous processes will demand rethinking of the old batch schedule. For determining the necessary minimal target runtime for a given failure rate and a certain goal of uptime of the facility we can plot those factors and end up with an almost exponential curve (Fig. 3(C)), meaning that one can compensate a higher daily failure rate with a longer target runtime and get the same uptime for the process, but only to a certain point.

This analysis can also be used to determine the use of the N-1 stage connected to the perfusion culture, and to investigate the possibility of using one N-1 stage to produce the inoculum for multiple perfusion reactors. We determined the use of the N-1 stage, which is at around 10–15% for a targeted process runtime of 90 days almost regardless of the daily failure rate assumed for the perfusion culture (Fig. 3(D)). As expected, depending on the specific scheduling in the facility, it is feasible to use a single N-1 stage to feed multiple production lines, especially for long planned process runtimes and low failure rates.

Influence of facility flexibility on uptime of perfusion cultures

In the model presented above, we assumed that the N-1 stage is always available as soon as the production process terminates resulting in a minimal delay. This represents a facility with a maximum in flexibility for both personnel as well as equipment availability. The need for rapid reallocation of resources can be reduced for the price of more downtime but the impact of such a strategy has to be quantified. We therefore calculated the loss in uptime for a production facility with three different scheduling scenarios for the N-1 stage: first, the scheduling as described above with maximum flexibility; second, a scheduling with an open slot for the N-1 culture every x days that can be used (called limited flexibility); and third, a completely restricted N-1 stage that is only available for the targeted process end (Fig. 4). Obviously, these strategies will lead to lower and lower uptimes for progressively more restricted scenarios, but the goal is to quantify the impact of each of these modes of scheduling. For implementation, the gained benefit for easier planning has to be evaluated for specific facilities individually, as for single-product facilities it might be feasible to implement a maximum flexibility approach,

while multi-product facilities with no dedicated equipment might need stricter planning.

The limited flexibility approach can be designed with more or less flexibility, as a schedule can allow for the start of an N-1 culture either each week, each second week or with an even longer periodicity. We investigated schedules of a free slot every 7, 14, 21 and 28 days. Depending on the day of the failure, the next N-1 culture can either start immediately (if the process failed on the day before a slot is available) or has to wait up to the periodicity of the schedule (if the process fails right after the slot was available). We simulated the impact of three different daily failure rates of 0.05%, 0.3% and 1% and show the uptime for 7, 14, 21 and 28 days scheduling for the N-1 stage for a planned process time of 90 days (Fig. 5(A)). As before, the influence on the uptime is dependent on failure rate, which is expected as the introduced additional restriction only affects processes that are terminated early. We can also see that choosing a reasonable periodicity of 1 or 2 weeks instead of maximum flexibility in the facility will lower the uptime in production from 94.6% to 93.3% for a periodicity of 1 week and to 92.3% for a periodicity of 2 weeks for a process with a daily risk of 0.3%. The gain in uptime for a maximum flexibility approach is therefore minimal for such processes and most certainly not worth the effort. Scenarios of periodicities of 2 weeks for N-1 taking 7 days or less, or a cycle of 4 weeks for N-1 taking 14 days or less might be especially interesting, as this enables the N-1 to feed two production lines without the chance of any scheduling conflict due to processes terminating early and with only minimal losses in uptime of the production train.

In the next step, we wanted to simulate the combined influence of flexibility of the N-1 stage with various planned process times, as for longer planned process times the ratio of processes terminated early is substantially larger. We selected a maximum flexibility scenario, limited flexibility with 7, 14 and 28 days periodicity and the very inflexible approach for a daily failure rate of 0.3% and simulated planned runtimes of up to 320 days (Fig. 5(B)). This analysis shows that for very short processes of 30 days, the influence is minimal, as almost all processes that are run actually make it to the 30 days mark. For processes that yield high uptimes above 90%, meaning processes run for 60 days or longer, the impact of increased flexibility is visible, but only substantial for a periodicity of 28 days. As expected, the inflexible approach is very unsuitable for continuous manufacturing, as the uptime is markedly decreased for runtimes above 45 days.

While these results were expected in general terms, they have not been quantified before and we can see that there is no necessity for a daily reallocation of resources for potentially failing processes. Already a minimal flexibility of being able to start an N-1 every other week is already enough to come very close to the optimum achievable through maximal flexibility and rapid resource reallocation. And any achievable flexibility, even if it is monthly, is already vastly beneficial to no flexibility at all. A monthly or biweekly reallocation of a seed fermentation will be possible for any biopharmaceutical production facility, and this analysis shows that the pressure to restart the production stage as soon as possible is not warranted in a continuous perfusion production setup and a more conservative planning and scheduling approach will not lead to any significant losses. For all subsequent analyses we assume a weekly availability of the seed stage, as we think this is an approach that can be realized in almost any biopharmaceutical facility and avoids the rapid daily reallocation of resources necessary for maximum flexibility.

Figure 4. Graphical representation of the different modes of scheduling for the N-1 stage and handling of early termination of the production process. Maximum flexibility assumes the N-1 reactor to be usable as soon as the production reactor fails. Limited flexibility assumed allocated starting time slots (e.g. each week on Monday) and the start of the N-1 stage must wait for a free slot. No Flexibility assumes that the N-1 is only ready on the target planned time point.

Influence of lot definition

How to define a lot in a continuously running system is a matter of ongoing debate. A hot topic is the implementation of real-time release based on online monitoring tools to maximize the product output and ensure full traceability of the product. This strategy allows the release of the product stream directly from the continuous production line and minimizing the output that has to be rejected in the case of a process disturbance by immediate detection of the deviation. No lot testing of the produced material after production is necessary. This maximizes the material that can be sold and minimizes cost in the analytical department, but current technology is not yet ready for implementing a complete real-time release. Approaches that are more conservative define a lot by a period of production time on an hourly, daily or weekly basis. While a longer period collected and defined as a lot reduces costs for testing of product quality, more material must be discarded in the case of any process failure. Efforts are being made in the scientific community to quantify the minimum that will have to be discarded through the modelling of residence time distributions through whole process trains showing a spread of minutes to

hours, depending on the unit operations and the length of the process train.²⁸

While real-time monitoring is a necessity for real-time release, the benefits in savings in the analytical department could also be realized without real-time release, enabling the combination with established analytical methods for lot-release testing. In this investigation we want to quantify the potential losses in product resulting from more conservative lot definitions that are possible to implement today. For this, we assume a continuous run with daily failure rates of 0.1%, 0.3% or 0.6%, in which the last lot before failure is discarded completely. We assume a lot definition of 1 h (representing real-time release), a lot definition of a day, or a week, progressively losing more material in the case of a failure. All scenarios assume an availability of the N-1 stage every week as discussed before, representing a medium flexibility in the production facility to handle failures.

Figure 6(A) shows nine curves of three different failure rates and three different lot definitions. For all definitions that do not include a real-time release, but daily or weekly definition and testing of lots, we see an optimum for the simulated uptime in terms of the selected planned process runtime, as the loss of material

Figure 5. (A) Influence of reduced flexibility represented by a longer periodicity between available slots for the N-1 stage for 0.05%, 0.3% and 1% daily failure rates for a planned process time of 90 days. (B) Relationship between different planned process times and different flexibilities (periodicity of free slots) implemented for the N-1 stage.

Figure 6. (A) Impact of different lot definitions (real-time release, daily or weekly) on the uptime of a continuous run planned for failure rates of 0.1%, 0.3% and 0.6% per day. (B) Impact of lot definition times between real-time release and 7 days in respect to daily failure rates of 0.1%, 0.3% and 0.6% for a planned process time of 90 days.

will become more and more significant if more and more lots fail. This optimum is at 60–120 days for a daily lot definition, and 45 to 90 days for a weekly lot definition. For a real-time release such an optimum does not exist, as longer target runtimes always mean higher uptime. Plotting the lot definition in days *versus* the uptime for a 90 days process, one can see a decrease in uptime for going to any daily lot definition from real-time release (Fig. 6(B)). While for a process with a daily failure rate of 0.1% the loss when implementing daily lots instead of real-time release is around 3%, and the loss for rates of 0.3% and 0.6% is already at 4% and 6%, respectively. Longer lot definition times are even worse, and a weekly lot definition will already reduce the uptime assuming a failure rate of 0.3% per day from 93% to 81%. From these data we can conclude that a continuous facility needs at least a day-to-day release of product to reduce losses to an acceptable minimum. A real-time release instead of a daily lot definition can gain an additional 3–5% of uptime, directly translating to additional revenue, but comes with the effort necessary for technology development and implementation as real-time release is hardly feasible with today's technology. For stable processes of 0.3% daily failure rate or below, the costs and additional challenges for real-time release might not be worthwhile and a day-to-day lot definition is sufficient. This analysis can also be used to estimate the potential impact of process analytical tools capable of determining a process deviation early or in real time as the loss of product is the delay time in detecting an error and/or the batch definition. From this we can also infer that a daily lot definition will need analytics suitably fast to detect failures in the process, as a daily lot definition, but analytics that take a week lead to an effective weekly

Figure 7. Comparison of uptime for batch and continuous processes, showing batch processes with high flexibility and low flexibility in the N-1 stage, and continuous processes with high flexibility, 1-week and 2-week cycle availability and no flexibility in the N-1 stage.

lot definition as failure will be detected with a one-week delay leading to the production of unsuitable lots until the analytical data come in. To model the potential additional benefits of PAT, tools for advanced process control for the reduction of failures leading to process termination are not modelled here and would need the inclusion of a mechanistic or statistic process model.

Comparison to batch manufacturing scheduling

In the previous sections, we compared different scheduling approaches for continuous operation in handling failures during process time. In this section we compare these results to a standard traditional batch-based process. For a typical fed-batch fermentation, we assume a production time of 12 days in the production stage, and the same requirements for the seed and cleaning as for continuous production, meaning that the N-1 fermentation will take 9 days and can be started in parallel to the fed batch, and that cleaning between batches will take 3 days. We also use the same failure rates as for continuous manufacturing, as those data are based on batch failure rates anyway. We use the same flexibility scenarios for the N-1 stage for batch processes as for continuous processes, assuming either maximum flexibility or a rigid scheduling. For batch processes we omitted the limited flexibility cases, as the difference between a possible N-1 start every 7 days and no flexibility at all is very small because of the short target process time for the production reactor of 13 days. In comparison to a continuous process, all failed runs, regardless of when they failed, have to be discarded completely, as only material from a successful completed run can be transferred to further processing in a batch-operated facility.

This investigation is conducted for completely flexible and non-flexible batch scenarios, and for no flexibility, maximum flexibility and 1- or 2-week periodic availability for the N-1 stage for continuous processes with a target process time of 90 days (Fig. 7). We see that the design of flexibility in the N-1 stage is for both continuous and batch processes only important for higher daily failure rates. We also see that the batch process is significantly more insensitive to reduced flexibility in the N-1 planning as the process is anyway very short. In comparison, the no flexibility approach in the continuous process again markedly reduces the uptime of the unit. A large difference in this dataset can be seen between batch and continuous operation in the resulting uptime with a loss of uptime of between 10% and 20% for batch operation depending on the scenario. This is because of two factors, with the main contribution being the generally lower uptime even under best conditions (13 days production with 3 days cleaning and setup represent an uptime of only 81.25%). The second contribution is

Figure 8. (A) Uptime for the entire process train at different downstream failure rates for a perfusion culture connected to three subsequent downstream unit operations and the uptime for the complete process train. (B) Influence of number of unit operations on the uptime of entire downstream train for a 90 day perfusion culture target.

from the difference between day 1 risk being significantly higher. This higher risk on day 1 also means that once the process is running, the continuous setup has significantly fewer 'day ones' to worry about, while the day-one event is a much more frequent occurrence in fed-batch production. From this comparison, we can see that a higher uptime for continuous production schemes is reached, even if only limited flexibility for continuous production is achievable in the facility. Only for high daily failure rates in combination with facilities that cannot implement any flexibility for the N-1 stage does the batch process option show a higher uptime.

Failures in integrated upstream and downstream production trains

In addition to the assessment of failure and managing strategies for upstream production, it is important to simulate the uptime of a whole process train in the case of a directly interconnected downstream unit. This analysis helps to understand the importance (or non-importance) of catastrophic failures occurring in the downstream in comparison to catastrophic failures occurring in the upstream on a more general level. While we assumed total failure and restart for the upstream in the case of any failure, in downstream this is usually not the case for disturbances as unit operations can be reset quite quickly. We characterize such a failure as an intermittent unavailability of the unit which produces either nothing or product that is not within specifications. We assume that resolving an issue in the downstream will be possible within 24 h, as this gives enough time for chromatography columns to be exchanged, setting up replacement pumps or exchanging filters outside of normal schedule. Start-up phases of downstream units are usually within minutes or hours, so we think the 24 h definition is sufficient and conservative to capture all necessary steps to restart the downstream unit for production.

While defining the length of interruption is fairly straightforward with the assumption of a 24 h downtime regardless of the reason, defining the rate of occurrence of such events is much more complicated and this might also be dependent on the specific unit operation in question. While at least limited data were available for batch failures in the upstream, to our knowledge there is no report in the literature on failure rates for downstream equipment during continuous or batch production. Due to the lack of available data, and because a number of the

forementioned causes of failure for upstream are actually directly applicable to downstream as well (like material or equipment failure), we assumed the risk for a failure event will be of the same order of magnitude for the downstream as for the upstream. To determine the uncertainty associated with that risk estimation, we use for this analysis a failure rate range for downstream unit operations of 0.1% to 3% daily. We calculated the impact for a process with three subsequent downstream unit operations and a fixed upstream daily failure rate of 0.3% (Fig. 8(A)) with the entire process train not producing any product if any of the unit operation is either restarted (upstream) or on intermittent unavailability (downstream). From these data, we can see that the addition of unit operations and their failure rate reduces the uptime. However, the overall impact is much less pronounced than for the upstream process, even for very high daily failure rates of 3%. The same is true for the number of downstream operations, which have an impact, but changing from a four-step process to a three-step process only changes the uptime of the whole process train from 91% to 92% for a daily failure rate of 0.6% (Fig. 8(B)). As the number of unit operations in the downstream has a much more significant impact on the total product yield of the process as well as on the cost of the process, the influence on the uptime of the process can be safely neglected.

CONCLUSIONS

In our simulations we were able to quantify the impact of different lot definitions and scheduling approaches for continuous manufacturing, especially the upstream production and scheduling of the N-1 seed train and compared this to the typical batch or fed-batch production for biopharmaceutical products. In the field of continuous biomanufacturing, much discussion is currently around meaningful lot definitions, real-time monitoring and release and scheduling and failure management. We were able to show that continuous biomanufacturing does not necessarily need real-time release or narrow lot definitions. A 24 h lot definition and a facility scheduled with limited flexibility, which can restart a failed process every 2 weeks, is only a few percent worse than a facility with maximum flexibility and real-time release. We showed that even when using such traditional and conservative approaches for the implementation of continuous biomanufacturing the productive uptime of the process is already

significantly better than that of batch-based processes. Additionally, we were able to identify a planned maximum runtime of 45–90 days for continuous upstream as the most beneficial if failure rates are considered. In conclusion, we provided a rational basis for assessing if real-time release is feasible and worth the large investment for continuous manufacturing, especially for upstream production. A very flexible reallocation of resources in the seed fermentation is not necessary to be able to benefit from continuous manufacturing, and limited flexibility is already able to alleviate scheduling issues of continuous manufacturing facilities with the inevitable failures in mind.

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